

Species Composition and Carbon Stock in Wasur Tropical Forest, Papua

Annisa Putri Amalia Ma'ruf (2010423003)- Teaching Laboratory 4 Biology
Department, FMIPA AndalasUniversity

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6792266(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6792266>)

Wasur National Park is one of the national parks in Indonesia. It is located in the southeastern part of Papua Province. His name is the name of one of the villages in it. The name comes from the Marori word Waisol which means garden. Wasur National Park is a wetland that is flooded for 4-6 months a year. In it there is a habitat for migratory birds. The balance of the ecosystem in Wasur National Park is influenced by the water cycle. In the dry season, swamps are formed as the water recedes through natural ditches connected to the sea. Wasur National Park is included in the Merauke Regency area in 4 sub-districts. These sub-districts are Merauke District, Jagebob District, Sota District and Naukenjarai District. The area within Wasur National Park is inhabited by four tribes, namely the Kanume Tribe, Yeinan Tribe, Mengey Marori Tribe and Marind Tribe. These four tribes live in customary forest areas. This research is a combination of plant and herb ecology which studies the composition of species and their effect on the carbon stock in the forest.

Forests are renewable natural resources and have a very important role in supporting ecosystem life. Indonesia is one of the countries that has the largest area of tropical rain forest in the world and the third country after Brazil and Africa (Achmaliadi 2001) which has high biodiversity. This high biodiversity can provide versatile benefits and has vital and strategic benefits, as the basic capital of national development and is the lungs of the world that are absolutely needed both now and, in the future, (Suhartini 2009). Tropical lowland forest is a type of forest ecosystem that occupies most of the mainland of Sumatra. Sumatran lowland forests have high biodiversity (Laumonier, 1997). Tropical lowland forests play an important role as a source of wood, germplasm reserves and medicinal ingredients, as well as providers of environmental services such as water management, erosion prevention, climate control and carbon storage (Sujarwo and Darma, 2011). Carbon Stock (Stock C) calculates with biomass approach, carbon dioxide absorbed by plants by photosynthesis is stored in the morphology of the biomass. The amount of carbon stock in the forest is estimated using the following equation (Murdiyarso dkk., 2004):

$$C = 0.5 \times W$$

Note:

C = carbon stock/store (kg)

W=treebiomass(kg).

Live tree biomass was estimated using the Ketterings allometric equation as follows (Hairiah and Rahayu, 2007):

$$(AGB)_{est} = 0.11 \times D^{2.62}$$

Note:

(AGB)_{est} = Live tree biomass (Kg)

D = Diameter of the tree (cm)

r = Density of tree (g/cm³)

Measurement of tree biomass was carried out using the non-destructive sampling method. Sampling was carried out on a permanent measuring plot (PUP) covering an area of 1 ha which was divided into 115 sub plots using the census method. All trees with a diameter of 8 cm (\pm 1.30 m from ground level) were measured for diameter and species names were

recorded. Then, the tree biomass was calculated using the Ketterings allometric equation based on the stem diameter (Suwardi dkk., 2013). Identification of plant species was carried out at the Andalas University Herbarium (ANDA). The identification process uses several literatures as references such as Backer, Corner and Watanabe, Heyne, Soerjani and Whitmore (Tribudiarti dkk., 2018).

The species level diversity of several of the plant communities are probably limited by poor soil fertility and moisture. Low soil fertility also may contain diversity in lowland hill forest communities at the site. When local soil condition and other factors are considered, the floristic communities present in the site suggest that savannah areas are probably natural (climax) communities, and not the result of historical human intervention such as fire-associated land clearing. Area of low land forest in Wasur tropical forest contains most complex and diverse biota at the site. This hypothesis is because it was found that research has been carried out in the forests in Papua as well, which results are as follows. During the survey, a checklist was compiled containing 412 plant taxa, 44 ferns and fern allies, 4 gymnosperms, 102 monocots and 262 dicots. At least five species were identified as new to science. Two additional species regarded as new have been forwarded to specialist currently revising the respective groups. There are also two survey specimens which may represent undescribed taxa, but which cannot be fully evaluated with existing information. Thus, a total of nine plant species from the survey at Tangguh, Papua (Salo, 2005).

Based on the research that done by Zulkifli and others (2011) in Papua, the natural succession area, the highest carbon biomass of 98.88 tons/ha was found in the B5BL area and the lowest was 30.64 tons/ha in the B12BB area. In the reclamation area, the highest carbon biomass was found in the Casuarina sp block with a total carbon of 530.77 tons/ha. The high carbon biomass is due to the stand diameter which tends to be large ($d > 18$ cm; Z; The high carbon biomass value in natural succession areas indicates the potential of tailings land as a substrate supporting the growth of vegetation that is organically growing. Reclamation is a form of company existence to accelerate heterogeneous forest formation.

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